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OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE USE OF DOPPLER SONOGRAPHY IN DENTAL IMPLANTOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the use of Doppler sonography to assess microcirculation in peri-implant tissues in patients undergoing dental implantation. The study analyzes the dynamics of vascular parameters and their correlation with osseointegration and bone density. The results confirm that Doppler sonography provides prognostic value for the success of implantation and early detection of complications.

Keywords: *dental implantation, Doppler sonography, osseointegration, microcirculation, bone density.*

Introduction

Dental implantology is one of the most dynamically developing branches of modern dentistry. The success of implantation depends on many factors, including

anatomical features, bone density, the quality of surgery and, most importantly, the state of local blood supply. One of the key factors for successful osseointegration is microcirculation in the implant tissues.

Traditional diagnostic methods — radiological and clinical — do not allow us to fully assess the dynamics of vascular changes. These methods provide only a static picture of the state of the bone tissue, but do not allow us to assess the functional activity of the blood supply. In this regard, the use of Ultrasound Dopplerography (UD) is a promising direction that can improve the accuracy of diagnosis, predict the results of implantation treatment and monitor effectiveness at each stage.

UD becomes particularly relevant in the context of an individual approach to treatment, where it is necessary to take into account the anatomical, physiological and even behavioral characteristics of the patient (including the presence of bad habits and concomitant somatic diseases).

The purpose and objectives of the study

The aim is to substantiate the use of Dopplerography in dental implantology as a method for monitoring microcirculation and predicting treatment outcomes.

Tasks:

1. The use of ultrasound before the installation of the implant to assess the initial vascular status;
2. Study of hemodynamic changes in the implantation area at different stages of healing;
3. Investigation of the relationship between blood flow and bone density;
4. Comparison of indicators in patients with upper and lower jaw implants;

Materials and methods

The study involved 12 patients (6 men and 6 women) aged 25 to 55 years who underwent dental implantation. The patients were divided into two groups:

- Group 1 — patients with partial secondary maxillary adentia;
- Group 2 — patients with partial secondary mandibular adentia.

The patients underwent a comprehensive examination, including a clinical examination, X-ray diagnostics, cone beam computed tomography and ultrasound Dopplerography. Vascular parameters were assessed using ultrasound imaging on a LOGIQ F8 device (GE HealthCare, Germany) equipped with a linear high-frequency sensor (6-15 MHz), which made it possible to obtain high-resolution images of vascular structures in the maxillofacial region.

The study parameters included:

- Vmax (maximum blood flow velocity) — reflects the peak speed of blood movement in the vessel;
- Vmin (minimum blood flow rate) — indicates the blood flow rate in the diastole;
- RI (resistive index) is an indicator of vascular resistance, calculated using the formula: $(V_{\max} - V_{\min}) / V_{\max}$;
- PI (pulsation index) — reflects the degree of pulsation of blood flow, calculated as $(V_{\max} - V_{\min}) / V_{\text{average}}$.

Conducting Dopplerography

The Doppler snapshot

In color Doppler mode, blood flow is displayed visually (blue — from the sensor, red — to the sensor).

The study was conducted in three stages: before implantation, on day 14, and 3 months after surgery. Additionally, densitometry was performed using the R2Guide digital program, which made it possible to quantify bone density on the Digital Air scale. These data were compared with the results of ultrasound to identify the relationship between hemodynamic parameters and structural restructuring of bone tissue.

The results of the study

The analysis of Dopplerographic indicators demonstrated the following dynamics:

- **After implantation**, there was a decrease in blood flow velocity (V_{max} , V_{min}) and resistance index (RI), which corresponded to an acute inflammatory response associated with surgical trauma;

- **On day 14**, there was a positive trend — restoration of blood flow, expansion of the vascular network and a decrease in vascular resistance (decrease in RI), which indicated the active phase of angiogenesis;

- **After 3 months**, the parameters returned to normal and became comparable to those in the intact areas, which was regarded as the completion of osseointegration.

When comparing the upper and lower jaw, it was found that:

- Hemodynamic recovery in patients with mandibular implants was faster;
- Signs of decreased blood flow persisted in the upper jaw area for longer, which required more careful monitoring in the postoperative period.

Intact teeth

The middle part

Medial

Distal

Transversal

Before implantation, the area of planned implantation

The middle part

Medial

Distal

Transversal

After implantation

2D X-ray

Doppler

Analysis of densitometry data one month after implantation revealed a slight increase in bone density in the implant area, indicating the beginning of remodeling

processes. On average, this indicator was 1.08 ± 0.06 g/cm². At first, patients limited the load on the implantation area, which could affect the dynamics of changes.

Three months after surgery, 12 patients showed a further increase in bone density, to an average of 1.18 ± 0.04 g/cm². characteristics of bone tissue.

The research stage	Average bone density in the area of intact areas	Average bone density in the implantation area	Density difference (%)
Before implantation	1,15 ± 0,06 (u/j) 1,25 ± 0,05 (l/j)	0,83 ± 0,05 (u/j) 0,98 ± 0,05 (l/j)	20% (u/j) 18% (l/j)
1 month after implantation	1,15 ± 0,06 (u/j) 1,25 ± 0,05 (l/j)	0,92 ± 0,05 (u/j) 1,08 ± 0,06 (l/j)	12,2% (u/j) 13,6% (l/j)
3 months after implantation	1,15 ± 0,06 (u/j) 1,25 ± 0,05 (l/j)	1,1 ± 0,04 (u/j) 1,18 ± 0,04 (l/j)	3,5% (u/j) 5,6% (l/j)

U/J - Upper jaw; L/J- lower jaw

A similar trend continued in the upper jaw, where the difference between bone density in the area of intact teeth and bone density in the implantation area decreased.

Conclusions

1. Ultrasound Dopplerography is an informative and non-invasive method of monitoring the condition of blood vessels in the implantation area.
2. The method allows you to monitor the vascular response to surgery, analyze angiogenesis and predict the effectiveness of osseointegration.
3. The inclusion of ultrasound in standard postoperative monitoring protocols promotes early detection of complications and individualization of treatment.
4. The combination of ultrasound and densitometry makes it possible to obtain an objective picture of both the functional and structural state of tissues.
5. The use of the technique increases the overall reliability and predictability of dental implantation.

Discussion

The use of Dopplerographic methods in dental practice opens up new horizons for a personalized approach in implantology. This method can become an important element of a comprehensive diagnosis, which makes it possible to evaluate not only the anatomical, but also the functional characteristics of the intervention area.

The results of this study emphasize the importance of vascular control in the planning and implementation of dental implantation, especially in difficult clinical situations and in patients with a complicated somatic status. The introduction of ultrasound into routine practice can help improve the effectiveness of treatment, reduce the incidence of complications and improve the long-term results of implantological therapy.

REFERENCES

1. Misch C.E. *Contemporary Implant Dentistry*. 3rd ed. Mosby, 2007.
2. Brunski J.B. *Biomechanical factors affecting the bone–dental implant interface*. *Clin Mater*. 1992.
3. Gvetadze R.Sh., Surov O.N. and others. *Assessment of vascular changes during implantation*. // *Dentistry*, 2015.
4. Losev F.F. *The use of Dopplerography in dentistry*. // *Bulletin of Dentistry*, 2019.
5. Artzi Z. *Bone density in the posterior maxilla: a comparative study*. *Clin Oral Implants Res*. 2004.
6. Jabborov A.U. Rustamova H.E. *Innovative research methods in dental implantology, collection of abstracts of the Republican scientific and practical conference “Day of Young Scientists”, 2024*.
7. Azimov A.M., Yunusova L.R., Jabborov A.U. *Study of blood circulation of the jawbones using Dopplerography*, 2024
8. Mannanov J.J., Nusratullayeva N. K., Jabborov A. U. *Osseointegration in dental transplantation*, 2024